

Predictors of Work Stress among Employees in Nepali Organizations

✉ Pralhad Adhikari

ABSTRACT

Work stress is the stress caused by various aspects of one's job or occupation. This study was conducted with the aim to identify the psychological predictors of job-related stress among Nepali employees working in various professions. Snowball sample was made by an online survey. There were 963 participants among which 500 were female ($M_{age}=25.6$) and 463 were male ($M_{age}=27.9$). Multiple regression analysis showed that job satisfaction, life satisfaction and two traits of personality significantly predicted work stress of Nepalese employees working in various industries. Neuroticism was common predictor of work-stress among healthcare, education, and security employees. Openness predicted work stress in teachers but extraversion predicted stress in medical professionals. The conclusion is that life and job satisfaction are needed to protect against work stress. Personality traits also lead to work stress. Extraversion is protective against but neuroticism is contributing to it.

Keywords: doctors, nurses, teachers, personality, extraversion, neuroticism, life satisfaction, job satisfaction, engineering

Introduction

The stress caused due to one's job, work or occupation is called work stress (Adhikari, 2020). When an employee's wellbeing is threatened or challenged by a situation at work, the psychological and physiological adaptive response adopted by them can be called work-related stress (McShane & Glinow, 2018).

Prevalence of occupational stress (or work stress or job stress) has been studied in a few industries in Nepal. Some rare studies show work stress as highly prevalent. Resident doctors had 64.5% burnout (Pokhrel et al., 2020). Alarmingly, 96% to 100% nurses experienced some form of stress (R. K. Mehta & Singh, 2015; Neupane et al., 2020; Paudel-Subedi, 2018). More than half of teachers were distressed (D. P. Kayastha & Kayastha, 2012). Gender is a cause of physical stress among them (Mondal et al., 1970). During COVID-19 pandemic, studies report that 25.4% (Silwal et al., 2020) to 53.5% healthcare employees (Kafle et al., 2021) had some forms of stress. A study found cent percent health care employees experiencing stress (Pandey et al., 2020).

The psychological predictors of job stress have been rarely studied in Nepal. Organizational constraints (like lack of resources), interpersonal constraints, low task control, and work overload (McShane & Glinow, 2018) have been attributed to work-related stress. Age and number of dependents predicted the stress among executive officers (R. Kayastha et al., 2013). Violence is a cause of stress among doctors (Magar, 2013). There was dependence of stress on age, marital status, over-time work, and working unit

✉ Assistant Professor, Tri-Chandra Campus

among nurses (Gurung et al., 2020; R. S. Mehta, 2017; Silwal et al., 2020). Security employees' stress was caused by poor management, work overload, inhumane treatment, and the lack of work-life balance, psychological support, proper grievance mechanism, and chances of refreshment (Kathmandu School of Law & Danish Institute for Human Rights, 2018).

This study contributes to the understanding of some psychological factors leading to the work stress in Nepalese employees. It also helps to figure out some predictors of job stress related to some industries like healthcare, engineering, white collar work, and security in particular.

Method

An internet-based survey tool named Google Forms was used to collect data by snowball sampling. The students of IO Psychology studying in the third year in a governmental college in Kathmandu, as research assistants, sent the link of the form to working individuals. Filling the form had been made voluntary with the information about survey presented at the beginning. The responses were downloaded when the count had reached 995. Thirty-two data were removed as they were filled by non-working persons. The data collection continued for 40 days during the last two months of 2021.

Instruments

Work stress questionnaire- revised (WSQ-R by Holmgren et al., 2009) was used to measure work stress. It consists of 21 questions. It has four themes- work interference with leisure time, indistinct organization and conflicts, influence at work and individual demands and commitment. Minnesota satisfaction questionnaire shorter version (MSQ by University of Minnesota, 1977) was used to measure job satisfaction. It has 20 items. It gives total scores in terms of general satisfaction and also scores for intrinsic and extrinsic satisfaction. Satisfaction with life scale (SWLS by Diener et al., 1985) was used to measure life satisfaction. Big Five Inventory- 44 items version (John & Srivastava, 1999) was used to measure the five traits of Big Five Model of Personality. It measures five traits – openness to experience (O), conscientiousness (C), extraversion (E), agreeableness (A), and neuroticism (N).

All the tests were translated to Nepali and they were administered in both the languages to the participants as languages presented in pure form would be incomprehensible to the participants. People in Nepal, particularly employees, generally use mixed language (Nepali language with some words of English) in daily conversation.

Some items related to sociodemographic variables were also included in the survey.

Participants

There were 963 participants among which 500 were female ($M_{age} = 25.6$) and 463 were male ($M_{age} = 27.9$). Participants ranged from 18 to 60 years in age. Five participants (0.50%) had education above master's degree. 148 participants (15.4%) had master's degree,

516 participants (53.6%) had bachelor's degree, 262 participants (27.2%) had high school degree, and 32 participants (3.30%) were just literate. Employees from various ethnicities participated in the study. Some of them were Bahun, Bam, Baniya, Bishwakarma, Bohara, Chhetri, Dalit, Damai, Danuwar, Dasnami, Dhami, Dhobi, Dura, Gajmer, Ghale, Gurung, Kaami, Kirati, Limbu, Madhesi, Magar, Majhi, Malah, Mali, Newar, Rai, Rajbanshi, Rajput, Rana, Sah, Sanyasi (Bharati, Giri), Sarki, Shahi, Sherpa, Sunar, Tajpuriya, and Tamang among others. Other characteristics of the participants are presented in table 1. T tests and one-way ANOVAs showed no significant difference between scores in life satisfaction, job satisfaction, and work stress based on types of characteristics mentioned in table 1. No significant difference was seen on five personality traits either on the very bases.

Table 1

Characteristics of participants and their scores on SWLS, MSQ, WSQ, and BFI.

Characteristic	Types	N (%)	SWLS M (SD)	MSQ M (SD)	WSQ-R M (SD)	O M (SD)	C M (SD)	E M (SD)	A M (SD)	N M (SD)
Sex										
	Female	500 (51.92)	22.43 (6.51)	74.93 (13.33)	15.32 (8.02)	36.63 (4.60)	34.10 (5.79)	26.33 (4.09)	34.86 (5.58)	22.43 (6.51)
	Male	463 (48.08)	21.90 (6.56)	74.79 (12.94)	16.00 (8.86)	36.32 (4.75)	34.08 (6.05)	26.40 (4.01)	35.27 (5.46)	21.90 (6.56)
SES										
	Poor	28 (2.91)	19.07 (8.23)	74.04 (14.82)	18.93 (10.82)	36.29 (4.00)	33.71 (6.19)	25.61 (4.38)	35.36 (4.34)	19.07 (8.23)
	Middle-class	923 (95.84)	22.28 (6.47)	74.92 (13.12)	15.55 (8.32)	36.48 (4.71)	34.13 (5.90)	26.40 (4.05)	35.03 (5.56)	22.28 (6.47)
	Rich	12 (1.25)	21.50 (5.81)	72.33 (10.54)	15.50 (10.67)	36.92 (3.29)	32.08 (6.67)	25.67 (3.52)	36.25 (5.14)	21.50 (5.81)
Smoking/Tobacco										
	No	860 (89.30)	22.22 (6.53)	75.07 (12.98)	15.80 (8.44)	36.53 (4.63)	34.20 (5.85)	26.40 (4.07)	35.01 (5.55)	22.22 (6.53)
	Yes	103 (10.70)	21.83 (6.59)	73.17 (14.38)	14.36 (8.34)	36.11 (5.01)	33.20 (6.35)	26.11 (3.92)	35.42 (5.33)	21.30 (5.68)
Alcohol										
	No	750 (78.13)	22.27 (6.51)	74.76 (13.33)	15.45 (8.37)	36.44 (4.77)	34.15 (5.89)	26.31 (4.06)	35.18 (5.54)	20.80 (5.48)
	Yes	210 (21.87)	21.80 (6.68)	75.40 (12.47)	16.16 (8.52)	36.63 (4.33)	33.92 (6.00)	26.55 (3.97)	34.67 (5.46)	20.69 (5.60)
Vegetarian										
	No	843 (87.54)	22.20 (6.55)	74.91 (13.32)	15.51 (8.51)	36.44 (4.75)	34.13 (5.96)	26.33 (4.01)	35.13 (5.60)	20.73 (5.48)
	Yes	120 (12.46)	21.97 (6.52)	74.76 (11.94)	16.41 (7.65)	36.77 (4.13)	33.95 (5.57)	26.64 (4.24)	34.66 (4.97)	21.09 (5.70)
Occupation										
	NA	60 (6.20)	21.17 (5.97)	72.47 (11.96)	15.92 (9.19)	35.12 (5.48)	32.00 (5.78)	25.88 (3.68)	33.18 (5.65)	21.92 (4.54)
	Business	22 (2.30)	22.86 (5.77)	76.55 (13.98)	16.36 (9.57)	35.77 (4.31)	32.73 (6.27)	26.05 (4.01)	34.05 (6.48)	21.55 (6.62)

Characteristic	Types	N (%)	SWLS M (SD)	MSQ M (SD)	WSQ-R M (SD)	O M (SD)	C M (SD)	E M (SD)	A M (SD)	N M (SD)
	Blue-collar work	14 (1.50)	20.64 (3.91)	75.79 (11.55)	14.86 (10.14)	36.57 (4.89)	34.86 (5.92)	27.29 (4.51)	36.86 (4.66)	20.14 (6.04)
	Engineering	74 (7.70)	21.59 (5.33)	74.30 (11.46)	15.80 (7.55)	36.31 (4.24)	34.22 (5.72)	27.03 (3.84)	35.23 (5.43)	20.81 (5.16)
	Medical	226 (23.50)	21.75 (7.07)	73.86 (13.90)	15.31 (9.17)	36.46 (4.85)	33.94 (6.26)	26.06 (4.14)	35.37 (5.51)	20.54 (5.79)
	Security	56 (5.8)	21.96 (6.61)	77.13 (11.77)	16.55 (8.41)	36.57 (4.00)	33.64 (5.64)	26.14 (3.90)	34.21 (5.89)	20.27 (5.80)
	Teaching	246 (25.5)	22.37 (6.81)	74.72 (13.23)	15.88 (7.72)	36.50 (4.66)	34.32 (5.84)	26.54 (3.83)	35.03 (5.50)	20.97 (5.19)
	White-collar work	265 (27.5)	22.82 (6.37)	75.90 (13.34)	15.42 (8.37)	36.87 (4.60)	34.62 (5.73)	26.42 (4.31)	35.36 (5.37)	20.65 (5.60)

Note. N=963. O means openness, C means conscientiousness, E means extraversion, A means agreeableness, and N means neuroticism in the BFI. NA means not answered.

In healthcare sector, doctor, HA, dental hygienist/surgeon, dentist, nurse, ANM, pharmacist, CMA, community health officer, optometrist, ophthalmologist, and lab assistant among others were included. In white-collar work, accountant, administrative employee, advocate, banker, beautician, manager, chef, copywriter, counselor, law intern, and civil servant among others were included. In engineering sector, there were engineer, suboverseer, and IT professional among others. In security sector, employees from army and police were included. In teaching industry, teachers teaching in school, college and university levels were included. In blue-collar work, farmer and construction worker were included. In business, businessperson, entrepreneur, auditor and CA among others were included.

Results

Life satisfaction and job satisfaction showed positive correlation. They both correlated negatively with work stress and neuroticism. Work stress correlated negatively with all big five personality traits except neuroticism. Table 2 shows the bivariate correlation between all variables of interest of this study.

Table 2
Correlation between major variables of the study

	SWLS	GS	O	C	E	A	N
SWLS							
GS	.484**						
O	.153**	.421**					
C	.223**	.428**	.535**				
E	.261**	.340**	.338**	.441**			
A	.110**	.351**	.521**	.677**	.324**		
N	-.245**	-.316**	-.314**	-.682**	-.436**	-.485**	
WSQ-R	-.320**	-.430**	-.149**	-.286**	-.199**	-.234**	.346**

Note. ** p?.01. GS means general satisfaction score of MSQ, O means openness, C means conscientiousness, E means extraversion, A means agreeableness, and N means neuroticism in the BFI.

Multiple regression analysis showed that 25.2% of variance is explained by the independent variables, $R^2 = .252$, $F(11, 923) = 22.23$, $p < .001$. Life satisfaction $B = -0.16$, $t(923) = -3.64$, $p < .01$, job satisfaction $B = -0.22$, $t(923) = -9.18$, $p < .01$, openness $B = 0.17$, $t(923) = 2.52$, $p < .05$, neuroticism $B = 0.36$, $t(923) = 5.83$, $p < .01$ significantly predicted work stress. Other variables considered were not statistically significant. They were conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, age, work hours per day, work days per week and number of jobs held by the employees. Table 2 shows the predictors of work stress across various professions.

Hierarchical regression analysis in two steps (first step with neuroticism and second step with life and job satisfaction as independent variables) showed that 12% variance is explained by neuroticism and life satisfaction and job satisfaction explained 12.5% variance. When the demographic variables were entered as covariates in the three-step hierarchical model, the model was seen as insignificant.

Table 3

Variables that significantly predicted work stress across various professions

Profession / Industry	R ²	F	Predictors	B	t	p value
Engineering (n=62)	0.29	2.36 (p?.05)	Life satisfaction	-0.27	-3.03	.008
Medical (n= 191)	0.28	7.07 (p?.001)	Life satisfaction	-0.27	-3.03	.001
			Extraversion	-0.37	-2.23	.027
			Neuroticism	0.30	1.98	.049
Teaching (n=212)	0.18	4.46 (p?.001)	Life satisfaction	-0.25	-3.34	.001
			Openness	-0.29	-2.22	.028
			Neuroticism	0.41	3.09	.002
White collar work (n=208)	0.23	-0.32 (p?.001)	Life satisfaction	-0.32	-3.48	.001
			Neuroticism	0.29	2.28	.024

Note. The professions with no significant predictors have not been reported here.

Discussion

Life satisfaction is a common predictor of occupational stress for various professions like engineering, teaching, healthcare, and white-collar work. Some personality traits also predict the work-related stress. Neuroticism predicts job stress for healthcare professionals, teachers, and white-collar workers. Extraversion predicts work stress among medical/healthcare professionals. Neuroticism predicts work stress in white collar workers.

Life satisfaction and job satisfaction protect against work-related stress. Personality trait of extraversion also prevents job stress for the Nepalese professionals. Neuroticism contributes to the work-related or occupational stress. Openness contributes to work-related stress but for teachers it is protective against stress.

Implications

As the basic OB model (Robbins & Judge, 2016, p. 36) has it, this study has verified that personality might be a cause of work stress. Because of personality difference, different people react to stressors differently (McShane & Glinow, 2018). For example, lower neuroticism and higher extraversion are related to lower job stress. Many models of stress present job or life satisfaction as consequence but they can also contribute to presence or absence of work stress. This thing can be concluded from this study.

This study has practical implications also. The organizations can hire employees low in neuroticism and high in extraversion for the jobs that are very stressful. Similarly, they can help increase the life satisfaction and job satisfaction so that employees get protected from work stress.

Limitations

The sample was made by snowballing technique. Most of the participants who volunteered to participate in it were relatively young. So, this research may not represent the condition of job-related stress of age group above 30 years well. The number of professionals from various industries was not proportionate. The study would be better with equal number of participants from all industries. The survey was long and took at least 15 minutes to complete. So, the participants might not have read the items to respond to carefully. This study limited itself to enquire some psychological factors but there are organizational and environmental factors that may act as stressors.

Future research

Personality characteristics other than those accounted in this study like hardiness (Ivancevich et al., 2014, p. 238) and positive self-concept (McShane & Glinow, 2018, p. 112) have been claimed to buffer employees' response to stress. These can be verified in Nepali culture and context. What factors account for the remaining 75% of variance of work-related stressor is an unanswered question. So, the future inquiries should be directed to find its answer. It has been touted that work stress to a certain extent is helpful and increases performance. The future studies should be conducted to verify this claim. Other negative consequences can also be inquired.

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लेख रचनाको लागि अनुरोध

यस आयोगबाट अर्धवार्षिक रूपमा प्रकाशित हुने निजामति सेवा पत्रिकामा लेख रचना प्रकाशित गराउन चाहने लेखक महानुभावहरूलाई आयोगमा प्राप्त हुने गरी लेख रचना पठाउन हार्दिक अनुरोध गरिन्छ । सार्वजनिक सेवा सम्बन्धी विविध पक्ष, आर्थिक गतिविधि र योजनावद्ध विकाससँग सम्बद्ध मौलिक, खोजपूर्ण, विचार प्रधान तथा अनुसन्धानमूलक विषय समावेश भएका लेख रचनाहरू प्रकाशनको निमित्त ग्राह्य हुनेछन् । प्रकाशनार्थ पठाइने लेख रचनाको सुरुमा सारांश, अन्त्यमा निष्कर्ष र लेखमा प्रयोग भएका सन्दर्भ सामग्रीहरू संलग्न भएको हुनुपर्नेछ । यस पत्रिकामा प्रकाशनको लागि पठाइएका लेख रचनाहरू अन्यत्र प्रकाशन गर्नुपरेमा प्रकाशकको पूर्व स्वीकृति लिनुपर्नेछ । पत्रिकामा प्रकाशनार्थ प्राप्त लेख रचनाहरू स्वीकार गर्ने वा नगर्ने अधिकार सम्पादक मण्डलमा रहनेछ ।

यस पत्रिकामा प्रकाशित हुने लेखहरूमा व्यक्त गरिएका विचारहरू लेखकका निजी विचार भएका हुनाले ती लेखहरूले लेखक कार्यरत वा लेख प्रकाशन गर्ने निकायको प्रतिनिधित्व गर्ने छैन ।

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